

COVID-19 Insights

Rapid Responsible Innovation in Times of Corona: Three Months Later

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Full citation to this publication:

Montiel, I.; Gutierrez, L. and Castillo, A. (2020): "Rapid Responsible Innovation in Times of Corona: Three Months Later". *Business & Society COVID-19 Insights*. Available at:

<https://businessandsociety.org/rapid-responsible-innovation/>

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